

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D3.6

Review of Communication and Dissemination Strategy

WP 3 – T3.2

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Abstract

This strategy outlines the approach for integrating and aligning activities under Task 3.2 of PARC, which focuses on communication, dissemination, and knowledge transfer. The strategy outlines a coherent framework to support and promote the visibility of scientific work carried out across the project by aligning communication efforts across different internal and external actors. A key objective is to enhance internal coordination and build synergies, ensuring that research outputs are not only scientifically sound but also reach the right audiences in accessible and impactful formats.

To achieve this, the strategy highlights the importance of co-creation, regular consultation with work package co-leaders and contact points, and close collaboration with the PARC coordination team. It provides guidance on how to formulate clear, evidence-based research messages, and how to tailor them to different target groups, including policy makers, researchers, stakeholders, and the general public. It also sets out practical mechanisms for identifying communication opportunities, supporting dissemination through national and European channels, and contributing to the overall strategic communication goals of PARC.

Moreover, the strategy underscores the importance of highlighting research results in a timely and coordinated manner, including through success stories, scientific outputs, and key messages with high societal relevance. These efforts aim to increase the visibility of PARC's achievements, support the uptake of scientific knowledge in policy and practice, and reinforce the long-term sustainability and impact of the Partnership.

This document presents the updated strategy (August 2025), building on the initial framework published on 31 October 2023. The revision reflects practical experience gained during the first phases of implementation, as well as feedback from partners and external reviewers. Key updates include enhanced mechanisms for internal coordination, clearer guidance on audience-specific messaging, and more actionable approaches to identifying and leveraging communication opportunities. These changes aim to strengthen the visibility and uptake of scientific outputs, ensure alignment across the project, and respond to evolving strategic needs.

Key Words

Communication, Dissemination, Engagement, Social media, Strategy, Risk communication

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List of abbreviations

AWPs: Annual Work Plans
CT: PARC Coordination Team (ANSES)EC: European Commission
EC DGs: European Commission Directorates-General
EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
EU: European Union
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GB: Governing Board
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
HBM: Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU: Human Biomonitoring Initiative for Europe
HRP: Horizon Results Platform
KPIs: Key Performance Indicators
KSOs: Key Strategic Orientations
MB: PARC Management Board
NGOs: Non-Governmental Organizations
NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment
NHs: National Hubs
NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points
OO: Operational Objectives
PARC: Partnership for the Assessment of Risk from Chemicals
RA: Risk Assessment
RM: Risk Management
R&D: Research and Development
R&I: Research and Innovation
SF: Stakeholder Forum
SO: Specific Objective
S2PD: Science to Policy Dialogue
WP: Work Package

1. Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to update the strategy for dissemination and communication activities outlined in Deliverable D3.2 and carried out during PARC. The communication and dissemination strategy is structured in sections addressing the different aspects that a communication plan may focus on: the strategy from the partnership to the external audiences, including the key messages, the communication tools and the elements needed to evaluate and measure the outreach of the communication strategy, as well as the basis for a proper internal communication between the partnership partners.

PARC's dissemination actions aim at communicating the project's objectives and outputs to a wide audience following a strategic plan to promote the adoption of the project's results and demonstrate its impact. It also intends to facilitate the exchange of information and the interaction not only with other related projects and initiatives but also with activities in industry, academia, and society as a whole.

Dissemination activities will be aligned with major milestones to maximise the impacts of the project and in strong interaction with all the other work packages.

The main objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy are:

- to ensure effective communication of the partnership messages and of the knowledge and outputs generated at local, regional, national and European level,
- to identify and make visible clear and simple messages related to the outputs of the partnership,
- to identify and map appropriate target groups to address the key messages to,
- to design and implement a wide range of tailor-made communication products using different tools and communication channels,
- to manage the social media accounts (Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram and X),
- to identify key performance indicators (KPIs) for dissemination, enabling the measurement of both the effectiveness and efficiency of the activities conducted, and to systematically track progress over time,
- to illustrate how the partnership will cooperate with other EC-funded projects or related initiatives and partnerships,
- to make the results of the partnership accessible, ensuring that they can be used by others and maximise the partnership's impact, by defining the dissemination and exploitation activities and
- to assist PARC partners to correctly implement the communication strategy.

2. Management and coordination of the communication strategy

Work Package WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness” is responsible for the dissemination of PARC results and will coordinate this task at consortium level. Specifically, task 3.2 is in charge of coordinating the communication, dissemination, and awareness activities.

Due to their role in consolidating, communicating, and disseminating results, the task 3.2 co-leaders — the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy in Hungary (NCPHP) — together with many partners involved in this task, will draw on the outputs of all other work packages (WPs) to raise PARC impact. At the same time, they will deliver services to the other WPs, by producing communication products to wide audiences.

Content to be included in targeted communication products will be developed in collaboration with the WPs involved in producing data, knowledge, and research outputs. Task 3.2 will provide support to the development and design of communication products, as well as to the formatting and editing of these materials.

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy is closely linked to the Annual Work Plans (AWPs) of PARC and is updated to ensure that along the Partnership the communication and dissemination activities support the implementation of each AWP.

3. Current situation: SWOT analysis from the communication perspective

A SWOT analysis helps ensure the communication strategy is realistic, focused, and responsive by identifying internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats that could impact success.

Table 1 – SWOT analysis of PARC from the communication perspective

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Communication/dissemination team with different competences and backgrounds. 2. Successful implementation of the previous project HBM4EU, namely at the communication level. 3. Addressing public health and environmental health topics with a clear impact on the society and a clear need for legislative change. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Complex scientific content may be difficult to communicate to non-expert audiences. 6. Project not widely known across all relevant sectors in every European country. 7. Timing of availability of project results affects negatively communication activities and message formulation.
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Development of a structured communication plan for a wide dissemination of the partnership mainly at 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Internal bureaucracy, reporting requirements and lengthy administrative processes, including procurement, can

<p>the SO1 level (but also supporting communication at national level).</p>	<p>slow down communication activities and reduce overall responsiveness and efficiency. 9. Complex decision-making and approval processes.</p>
<p>Opportunities</p> <p>10. Establishing new networks and strengthening cooperation within the academic community in the field of chemical risk assessment (chemical RA). 11. Opportunity to reach all participating countries and the EU. 12. Press and media coverage. 13. Strong online presence. 14. Technology can work in the project's favour. 15. Use data visualization and storytelling approach to effectively communicate PARC's story. 16. Dissemination of project results to various audiences: project partners, scientific community, policy makers, general public, and other stakeholders. 17. Stakeholder Forum involvement as a key player for dissemination of PARC's results. 18. Develop/implement new communication products or processes (podcasts, videos...).</p>	<p>Threats</p> <p>19. Scientific topic that is unlikely to reach or be properly understood by a wider audience. 20. Challenges related to data sharing and privacy policies. 21. Lack of successful stakeholder engagement. 22. Conflicting interests among stakeholders and partners may delay or hinder dissemination of results. 23. Substantial coordination work and follow-up required due to the involvement of numerous partners. 24. Partnership results may not be available when communication products need to be delivered. 25. Citizens' limited trust in chemical risk assessment and risk management processes.</p>

4. PARC goals and communication objectives

4.1. Horizon Europe framework and PARC

The policy priorities and the expected impact for Horizon Europe are described in the Strategic Plans. The first Strategic Plan sets out the key strategic orientations for the targeting of investments in the programme's first four years (2021-2024). The Strategic Plan aims to promote consistency between the work programmes, EU and national priorities, and to achieve continuity and coherence of funding measures.

The following four key strategic orientations (KSO) were identified in the first Strategic Plan:

- A. promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital, enabling and emerging technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations;
- B. restoring Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment;
- C. making Europe the first digitally enabled circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems;

- D. creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society, prepared and responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health care, and empowering all citizens to act in the green and digital transitions.

The key strategic orientations of the Horizon Europe programme are reflected in the objectives of PARC. PARC contributes to the goals of “Living and working in a health-promoting environment” calls, working towards the KSO-D ‘Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society’ of Horizon Europe’s Strategic Plan 2021-2024. Research and innovation (R&I) supported under this destination should contribute to the impact area ‘A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats’ and to the following expected impact set out in the Strategic Plan for the health cluster: ‘living and working environments are health-promoting and sustainable thanks to better understanding of environmental, occupational, social and economic determinants of health’. In addition, R&I supported under this destination could also contribute to the following impact areas: ‘Good health and high-quality accessible health care’, ‘Climate change mitigation and adaptation’, and ‘Clean and healthy air, water and soil’. PARC specifically falls under the call ‘Partnership in health’.

There is a new strategic plan for Horizon Europe 2025–2027. Given the continued relevance of the areas covered by the previous key strategic orientations and the new developments, the following key strategic orientations for R&I are defined for 2025–2027:

- the green transition;
- the digital transition; and
- a more resilient, competitive, inclusive, and democratic Europe.

In line with these priorities, the PARC communication strategy also takes these strategic orientations into account. As a partnership strongly focused on structuring an interface between science and public policy, PARC aligns with the new priorities set out by the European Commission for the 2024–2029 period. As the Commission emphasises the importance of reducing dependency on external resources and improving our capacities of resilience, PARC’s focus on chemical safety and innovation aligns with Europe’s drive to strengthen its industrial base.

By advancing the development of safer and more sustainable chemicals, PARC helps foster a competitive chemical industry that is resilient and able to meet both regulatory standards and market demands. At the same time, PARC contributes to strategic autonomy by promoting research and development within Europe, ensuring that the EU has control over the technologies and solutions critical to its economy.

4.2. PARC objectives

The objectives of PARC have been described in the Project proposal – Technical description (Part B). The general objective of PARC is to consolidate and strengthen the EU’s R&I capacity for Chemical Risk Assessment (CRA) to protect human health and the environment. In total, 13 realistic, measurable, achievable and verifiable operational objectives (OO) were defined under three specific objectives (SO).

The specific and the operational objectives are:

SO1. EU and national risk assessors and regulatory entities come together with the scientific community in a cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA.

OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC.

OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NHs).

OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy.

OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge.

OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives.

OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/ awareness of chemical RA.

SO2. European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemical RA.

OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes.

OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes.

OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA.

OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake.

SO3. European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA.

OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

OO11: Consolidate existing and developing new networks of laboratories and research centres.

OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

4.3. PARC communication objectives

Both strategic and tactical communication efforts are needed to share a common understanding of PARC. This will contribute to achieving the vision and ambition of PARC.

Table 2 summarises the PARC communication objective organised by three levels: societal, EU and PARC level.

Table 2. PARC communication objectives, considering three objectives' levels.

Objective level	Communication goal	Comments
Societal level	To ensure that the impact of PARC is recognised as one of the important accelerators of the development of new technologies and sectors like the chemical RA and Risk Management (RM), and crucial in steering the green transition.	<i>Horizon Europe framework</i>
	To ensure that citizens are empowered in the green transition as well as contributing to a more resilient, inclusive, and responsive Europe.	<i>Horizon Europe framework</i>
	To ensure a common and shared understanding of what PARC is about and why PARC has been established.	<i>Reflecting PARC's ambition and vision</i>

	To continuously promote PARC's different activities, covering all the work done in the WPs by making the results of the partnership accessible.	<i>Reflecting PARC's ambition and vision</i>
	Raise public awareness and public literacy with regards to chemical exposure, providing insights into possible behavioural changes that can reduce chemical exposure and improve health and well-being.	<i>SO1, SO2 and SO3</i>
	Ensure trust and trust ability towards PARC and the knowledge provision from PARC.	<i>SO1, SO2 and SO3</i>
	To ensure that all the key research findings are communicated with the society in an understandable and accessible language.	<i>SO1, SO2 and SO3</i>
	Engage with societal actors and public focus groups to better understand societal concerns regarding chemical exposure and awareness of chemical RA.	<i>SO1, SO2 and SO3</i>
EU policy level	Build a bridge between science and policy through continuous dialogue and engagement between individuals involved in cutting edge scientific research and individuals involved in all stages of chemical risk assessment and management.	<i>SO1, SO2 and SO3</i>
	To communicate the priorities for R&I in chemical RA, and RM with key stakeholders including regulators, national chemical RA and RM authorities, policymakers, etc.	<i>SO1, SO2</i>
	Communicate effectively with target audiences to ensure policy uptake.	<i>SO1, SO3</i>
	To achieve a change of practice (in regulatory uptake and use) and through implementation of new and innovative chemical RA methods.	<i>SO1, SO3 Knowledge production and new methods do not necessarily change practice and needs to be addressed continuously to achieve a step-by-step change.</i>
	To ensure that models and innovative concepts are contributing to S2PD the need to be both accessible, easily understandable, and useable.	<i>SO2</i>
	To raise awareness of, knowledge about, and the use of the tools facilitating knowledge uptake.	<i>SO3</i>
	Strengthen the perceived trust and trust ability in the partners involved in the production and dissemination/distribution of the different tools.	<i>SO3</i>
PARC level	Foster stakeholder engagement in PARC, so that stakeholders can contribute to disseminating and exploit our results in their own activities as well as promoting synergies amongst all.	<i>SO1</i>
	To ensure a shared understanding of, and approach to, FAIR data practices among PARC partners by addressing	<i>SO2</i>

	both the added value and the importance of “our shared political and social mission”.	
	To ensure that the training programmes are available to any potential stakeholder interested in the topics.	SO3
	To facilitate the exchange of information amongst all PARC members.	SO3

5. Expected impacts of the PARC project

The communication and dissemination strategy will contribute to the delivery of a number of expected impacts from the PARC partnership. PARC will involve several structures which will play an important role in helping towards the achievement of the expected impacts, namely at the policy/societal, scientific, and economic levels (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Representation of the three levels of PARC impact.

The **policy/societal impacts** of PARC will be the endorsement of innovative approaches in chemical RA at national, EU and international level and to reinforce the citizens, workers, and stakeholders' trust in science and how regulations protect humans and the environment. The communication and dissemination strategy will contribute to the achievement of the destination 2 'Living and working in a health-promoting environment' expected impacts by enabling policymakers and regulators to be better informed about chemicals as environmental, socio-economic and occupational risk and health promoting factors by increasing awareness and understanding of scientific evidence and chemical RA procedures. Through the communication of PARC activities and dissemination of results, PARC will also contribute to citizens' understanding of environmental and health issues, the measures to address them, and of the related policies and regulations to protect them and their environment. Concerning the national scale, the NHs will be of utmost relevance for the dissemination of PARC interests and outputs and to raise citizens' awareness. To assess success, a number of interactions with citizens/stakeholders will be used as indicators. This level will be addressed by communicating and disseminating project data including reports in non-scientific media, outreach/awareness raising activities, interactions with stakeholders, website/social media use.

The **scientific impact** of PARC will come from the achievement of PARC's SO2: 'European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment'. To promote PARC at national, EU and international levels, fundamental scientific results will be communicated through appropriate channels such as publications in peer-reviewed journals, and presentations at international conferences and workshops. By disseminating knowledge through systematic application of open science, R&I activities will be able to deliver results and knowledge corresponding to the needs of end-users. This way, PARC will contribute to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen's health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

The **economic impact** of PARC will result from the achievement of our SO3: 'European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical risk assessment'. The communication and dissemination strategy will contribute to the delivery of this objective by fostering communication across the stakeholder groups.

The contribution of PARC to the defined outcomes and widened of impacts, and the activities implemented to maximize these, will be followed closely throughout the partnership to measure its performance and ultimately to provide a robust justification for the long-term sustainability of PARC's activities. PARC's impact pathway is defined in its monitoring frame to provide a qualitative and quantitative-based indication of the scale and significance of PARC's contribution to the expected outcomes and impacts.

Under task 1.3 'Impact evaluation and monitoring of the performance indicators of the partnership', a comprehensive set of indicators has been developed, including defined baselines and clear targets. The framework comprises 12 output indicators (quantitative), 8 outcome indicators, and 8 impact indicators (both quantitative and qualitative), most of which are updated annually.

Each indicator is directly linked to PARC's operational, specific, and general objectives, enabling effective tracking of progress and achievements across the partnership. To structure this monitoring, PARC's specific impact goals - as outlined in the Biennial Monitoring Report (BMR) - are organised into three distinct impact pathways: (1) policy and societal impact, (2) scientific impact, and (3) economic impact. Each impact goal is supported by at least one output, outcome, and impact indicator.

Output indicators capture measurable data related to the performance of PARC activities and the products generated. These include, but are not limited to, the number and profile of PARC partners, projects, collaborations, trainings, publications, and developed datasets. Output indicators are primarily quantitative.

Outcome indicators reflect the immediate effects and results stemming from the outputs, often extending beyond the partnership itself. These may include collaborations with external stakeholders, dissemination of findings, development of methodologies, and stakeholder-targeted activities. Outcome indicators comprise both quantitative and qualitative data.

Impact indicators assess the broader, long-term influence of PARC. These include the uptake of PARC results in policy processes, the availability and use of tools and data, the societal and scientific reach of PARC publications, and citizen engagement. Impact indicators are predominantly qualitative. Further information [here](#).

To communicate PARC's progress and impact to a broader audience, a selection of data from the indicator framework is visualised by task 3.2 and made available on the PARC website (www.eu-parc.eu/indicators). On the website, data are organised by impact pathway (Policy and Societal, Scientific, and Economic), rather than by individual indicators.

The visualisation and publication process are ongoing, with continuous development of updates. In the meantime, the collected data are also summarised and shared in communication leaflets.

6. Defining our audience: who are we talking to?

6.1. A stakeholder mapping and engagement plan

This section includes a strategy for engaging with stakeholders which aims to promote their active participation in PARC. Engagement implies that the targets do not merely receive information, but that they contribute to the understanding and exploitation of PARC results. PARC stakeholders will have the opportunity to influence the prioritisation and decision-making process and shape outcomes, increasing their capacity to exploit our results. National Hub Contact Points should be contacted to identify key stakeholders at national level and build a list of stakeholders in the partner countries.

Stakeholder engagement approaches depend on the level of interest and the level of influence of the stakeholder. The higher the influence and the interest of the stakeholder are, the greater the investment in their participation should be. Figure 2 below illustrates the relationship between stakeholder influence and the investment in stakeholder engagement.

Certain stakeholders can act as multipliers of PARC messages. By reaching out to their constituencies and to the public, stakeholders have the potential to disseminate PARC messages to a larger audience and to increase PARC visibility. European level stakeholders with extensive networks in the Member States can access audiences at the national level. Such stakeholders can also gather input from their constituencies to feed into project activities, so increasing the credibility and legitimacy of PARC.

Figure 2. Relationship between stakeholder influence and approaches to stakeholder engagement: ‘joint ownership’ means high influence and high interest, ‘committed’ – high influence, low interest, ‘engaged’ – low influence and high interest, and ‘aware’ – low influence and low interest.

This is why a stakeholders' mapping is a crucial part of the strategy, which is a collaborative process of research, debate, and discussion that draws from multiple perspectives to determine a key list of stakeholders across the entire stakeholder spectrum. Mapping comprises four phases:

- E. Identifying: listing relevant groups, organisations, and people;
- F. Analysing: understanding stakeholder perspectives and relevance;
- G. Mapping: visualizing relationships to objectives and other stakeholders;
- H. Prioritising: ranking stakeholder relevance and identifying issues.

In this way, communication objectives can be clearly identified, and messages can be tailored to meet the needs of external stakeholder groups. Based on their potential influence on and interest in PARC, four categories have been identified.

- The **'Manage closely'** category includes stakeholders with potentially high interest in and high influence on the project. These are the 'Key players', which are individuals and organisations we aim to prioritise, investing the most time in communicating with them and managing the relationship closely.
- The **'Monitor/ minimum effort'** category includes 'Keep in Radar' stakeholders with potentially low interest and low influence. These stakeholders require minimal engagement, and we will mainly monitor them, devoting limited time and resources.
- The **'Keep satisfied'** category includes those with high influence but low interest. For this group, our communication focus will be on ensuring they remain positively engaged and supportive, even if their day-to-day involvement in the project is limited.
- The **'Keep informed'** category consists of stakeholders with high interest but low influence. These stakeholders value project outcomes and should be regularly updated with accessible and engaging information to maintain their interest and connection to PARC.

Figure 3. Stakeholders mapping

It is likely that some of these audiences will become influential and have a greater or lesser interest in PARC over time and depending on their interaction with the partnership.

6.2. Target audience

To achieve the main objectives and ensure that PARC results are exploited and generate impact, task 3.2 will need to disseminate its outputs and actively engage with a broad range of end users at national and international levels. These end users can be categorised under the following groups: researchers, policymakers, EU authorities/regulators in the field of chemical risk assessment, citizens, risk assessors and managers, industry, consumers and worker associations and many other groups indirectly involved.

When thinking who PARC audience is, the following questions matter:

- Does PARC have one or multiple audiences?
- Are there any communication barriers such as language or trust?
- What are their values and priorities?
- What might PARC have in common with the audience?

It is also important to decide who is the most influential. A small number of powerful advocates can make big things happen and task 3.2 is continuously working to identify these groups. The smaller and more clearly defined a target group is, the easier it becomes to develop focused communication that will really influence them. Nowadays people are more likely to be influenced by 'people like us' than by traditional voices of authority. Table 3 summarises the different communications tools envisaged considering the different stakeholders. To satisfy the different levels of engagement as shown in figure 2 several communication tools per stakeholder group are necessary.

Table 3. Communication tools and channels needed tailored to different type of audiences.

Level	Audience	Communication tools and channels
Political level	Regulatory bodies Risk assessors and risk managers National chemical risk assessor and risk managers authorities European Commission European Commission DGs Policy makers Members of the European Parliament and national members of Parliament National ministries responsible for public health, environment, labour, occupational safety and research Parliamentary Working Group Think tanks National Hubs Contact Points Regional institutions International organisations (WHO, UNEP....)	Policy briefs / newsletters Press releases Conferences / webinars Reports Website Social media Face to face meetings
Scientific level	International experts International bodies Scientific advisors Scientific societies and associations Scientific community Universities and research groups National research institutes in the field of public health and environment R&D groups in industry/private companies	Scientific papers Website Conferences / workshops Webinars Science Digest Newsletter Network meetings Brief on tools developed

	Other European projects and initiatives in the field of risk assessment and chemical safety Other relevant European networks (i.e., NRLs, metrology, etc)	
Industry level	EU Industry representatives and associations, including members of SF (Stakeholder Forum) SMEs in the field of chemistry Health insurance industry and the health sector Start-ups in the field related to chemicals, health and environment Trade unions	SF meetings, other stakeholder groups formed in the framework of various project activities Brief on tools developed and other products that will be developed
Innovation level	R&D Departments from both public and private sector	Webinars / conferences Website Stakeholder Forum Newsletters / policy briefs Videos Scientific papers
Societal level	Health professionals including gynaecologists and paediatricians (to reach pregnant women) Schools (to reach children and teenagers) Consumers' protection agencies Consumers Citizens associations (including vulnerable groups) and general public NGOs PARC survey participants Media	Website (and especially the citizen's microsite) Videos / visuals Webinars Leaflets, factsheets and infographics Press releases / media interaction Key messages – scientific outcomes

To support the internal communication within the consortium, the CT maintains a contact database of over 2000 PARC members. Filters can be applied based on various criteria, including organisation, country, roles in PARC boards and committees, involvement in specific work packages or tasks, participation in the network of the NHCPs and areas of expertise (when provided). This contact list allows information to be delivered to the relevant PARC members.

Additionally, the CT has started a mapping exercise to identify relevant external projects and expert committees that could serve as potential target audiences for future PARC communication products. This process began with analysing the internal library of Project Description Documents (PDD), which project managers complete when proposing a new PARC project. One of the sections of the PDD is called "Project Link Outside of PARC", where project managers can list external projects or initiatives that might be related to the PARC project they are proposing (e.g. Horizon Europe, Horizon 2020, international/national monitoring programs, etc.), relevant policy frameworks (e.g. Save and Sustainable by Design, One substance-One assessment, etc.) and committee/expert group that may be interested in the result of the project or might be doing a similar project (e.g. the OECD, ECHA's Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC), ECHA's Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL), EFSA's working groups, etc.).

Classifying the information provided according to these categories allows the CT to produce tailored lists that support the work of various PARC Tasks. For example, the list of the different committees and expert

groups is currently used by WP2 “A common science-policy-agenda” to identify the target audiences for policy briefs and research briefs developed in collaboration with WP3. This ensures that PARC results are effectively communicated to those with the mandate or capacity to use them in policy or scientific decision-making. Another use of this mapping exercise is to support task 3.3’s effort in establishing synergies and collaborations with external projects in the field of chemical risk assessment through SYNnet. By identifying relevant initiatives, task 3.3 can proactively propose bilateral meetings and initiate structured collaboration plans with aligned projects and organisations. With the support of the EEA’s Brussels Liaison Office, task 3.2 undertook a mission to Brussels, which significantly enhanced the visibility of PARC and provided actionable insights to shape future communication strategies. During a three-day visit, we engaged directly with key players in the EU policy and science communication ecosystem, including the Scientific Advice Mechanism linked to Science Advice for Policy by European Academies (SAPEA), the STOA Panel with the Scientific Foresight Unit, the European, Science-Media Hub, communication officers from DG Environment, DG RTD, as well as representatives from ECHA and EFSA. These interactions offered valuable perspectives on the information needs of EU policy actors and strengthened PARC’s standing as a credible voice in science-to-policy communication. A clear takeaway from the mission was the strong demand for succinct, accessible communication—delivering clear facts, concise figures, and actionable knowledge to support informed policy decisions.

In Q4 2025, a mapping survey exercise will be launched to better understand the communication needs and preferences of key stakeholders relevant to PARC. The target audiences include EU policy-makers in Brussels, national and EU-level regulators, and industry/business representatives.

The objective of this survey is to gather insights on:

- what types of information stakeholders find most useful;
- preferred communication formats (e.g., briefs, infographics, webinars);
- trusted sources and channels for scientific information;
- timing and context in which they use research outputs;
- perceived gaps in current communication efforts from PARC.

The results will inform the development of tailored communication strategies and products that are more relevant, timely, and impactful for each stakeholder group. This exercise is part of PARC’s broader aim to strengthen the link between science and policy and ensure that its findings contribute effectively to regulatory and decision-making processes.

7. Key messages

7.1. Key messages based on the PARC objectives

To achieve the greatest impact, a scientific message should ideally be tailored to the specific audience and communication goal.

At this point, it makes sense to limit the number of key messages to keep the vision clear. Currently, the dissemination of deliverables and results is in full swing, and all PARC communication products are tailored to the target audience, with clear and concise messaging.

The proposition may be supported by the top-line messages - the most important points PARC wishes to convey to the audience. Crucial questions to consider at this stage are:

- What are the key messages we wish to communicate?

- How do these messages relate to and support each other?
- Are these messages short, jargon-free, concise and meaningful?

The table 4 serves as an illustrative example to demonstrate how messages are formulated based on the specific target audience. It highlights the importance of adapting communication not only to the needs and expectations of different stakeholder groups, but also in alignment with defined communication objectives. Crucially, these objectives are directly linked to the overall goals of PARC, ensuring that all messaging supports the broader impact, visibility, and relevance of the project.

Table 4. Examples of messages based on the target group, communication objective and overall PARC objectives.

Project objectives	Communication objectives	Target group	Messages
SO1: EU and national risk assessors and regulatory entities come together with the scientific community in a cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA			
OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC	Promote the uptake of PARC results	Governing Board	PARC is vital to the empowerment of all citizens in the green transition as well as contributing to a more resilient, inclusive, and responsive Europe.
OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH)	Influence behaviour	National Hubs Regulatory bodies Policy makers	PARC will provide ad-hoc evidence-based strategies and tools for policymakers and regulators as well as active engagement.
OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy	Evidence based, Exposure & drugs	Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	Strategies employed to develop PARC are evidence based. Focus of PARC activities are reactive to identify regulatory priorities and new challenges.
OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge.	Influence behaviour	Regulatory bodies Policy makers Parliamentary WG Think tanks	An update on legislation is crucial for implementation of NGRA.
OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives.	Raise visibility of PARC project	International experts International bodies Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	PARC is harvesting the knowledge of a broad scientific community.
OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA.	Raise awareness of chemical risk assessment and influence behaviour	General public, Professional risk communicators, health professionals	Next generation of risk assessment will elevate citizen and consumer protection.
SO2: European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals RA			
OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes	Alignment,	Governing Board National Hubs Regulatory bodies	The annual R&I work programme is developed collaboratively, ensuring research activities address agreed

Project objectives	Communication objectives	Target group	Messages
	Stakeholder engagement, priority setting	Policy makers, Scientific advisors Scientific community	priorities and deliver maximum policy and societal impact.
OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes.	Increase understanding	Regulatory bodies Policy makers Parliamentary WG Think tanks Consumers' protection agencies Consumers Citizens associations NGOs	PARC is a continuation of HBM4EU, which generates knowledge to inform the safe management of chemicals and so protect human health in Europe.
OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA.	Increased understanding	International experts International bodies Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	Principles of FAIR data are applied to all the steps in PARC activities.
OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake.	Raise visibility	Regulatory bodies Policy makers Parliamentary WG Think tanks	PARC contributes to preventing negative effects of hazardous chemicals in the circular and sustainable production system.
SO3. European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA.			
OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.	Raise visibility	Industry Including members of SF (stakeholder forum)	PARC supports innovation in chemistry while reducing risk for health and the environment.
OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centers.	Influence behaviour	Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	PARC operates by building up and sharing knowledge and capacities.
OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.	Strengthen the perceived trust and trust ability in the partners involved	International experts International bodies Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	The NGRA resulting in PARC activities will be implemented by trained professionals.

7.2. How do we formulate key messages?

7.2.1. Key messages extracted from scientific publications

Scientific publications produced under PARC activities are compiled in the monthly Science Digest. Their key findings are translated into tailored messages - up to five for policymakers and one for regulators - in alignment with EU legislative priorities such as the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability.

To ensure technical accuracy while meeting the needs of policy audiences, task 3.2 collaborates closely with scientists involved in other tasks throughout the process. Readers can access these messages by clicking the “key message” button linked to each publication in the Science Digest.

Task 3.2 has also begun using AI-supported tools, including persona-based modelling, to refine messages based on the roles and priorities of the different audiences. Looking ahead, we plan to develop tailored key messages for citizens, specifically designed for dissemination via social media.

7.2.2. Key messages included in the research projects

Each internal research project published on the website features 3–5 key messages at the top of the page, provided alongside the research findings. These messages are initially drafted by the lead researchers, then reviewed and refined by WP3 for tone, clarity, and relevance to the target audience, and finally validated by the research owners before publication. These messages are initially drafted by the lead researchers, then reviewed and refined by WP3 for tone, clarity, and relevance to the target audience, and finally validated by the lead researchers before publication.

The final messages are designed to be reused across multiple channels, including policy briefs, news items, and public updates.

7.3. How are research messages formulated in PARC?

Effectively showcasing the scientific findings from PARC is essential to ensure their visibility, understanding, and uptake by key audiences such as policymakers, regulators, and the broader public. This section outlines the process of identifying, prioritising and transforming research messages into communication products.

7.3.1. Work Package (WP) contributions

Each WP identifies high-impact research findings suitable for policy communication. These typically include results with direct regulatory relevance, those that raise public health concerns, or those offering new methodological insights, which are then used for policy briefs.

For the policy brief dissemination strategy, led by WP2 and the CT, several key elements are being considered to maximise impact. These include identifying the regulatory gap(s) to prompt more specific and actionable input and clearly stating the policy relevance by outlining which policies the brief supports and why. A timeline aligned with the policy cycle is also considered, to determine when each brief will be most influential. Additionally, precise segmentation of the target audience, —such as differentiating between EU institutions, national authorities, and other stakeholders — enables more tailored communication. To better align with public interest, the inclusion of societal concerns is recommended, alongside more explicit planning for dissemination channels, including media and other public-facing

platforms. Finally, the briefs will feature a section with key policy messages that are concise, action-oriented, and directly relevant to policymakers, framed around clear implications and recommendations.

7.3.2. News items from the Management Board (MB) meetings

WPs are encouraged to regularly submit brief news items at each MB meeting, summarising new results, outcomes of meetings, key milestones from ongoing fieldwork or forthcoming publications. These updates serve as a dynamic pipeline for identifying potential topics for policy briefs and other communication products. The feedback from Task 3.2 of the previously published news items is also available on the MB annotated agenda.

8. Communication tools

As previously referred, when profiling target groups for such a wide and heterogeneous audience, it is critical to tailor communication products to the relevant audiences. These products must be made accessible and comprehensible to all identified target groups, by considering factors such as varying levels of technical understanding in the different socio-cultural contexts involved. The communication strategy relies on a coherent yet differentiated set of communication tools, with each product tailored to meet the specific needs of different end users and audiences.

An extensive use of graphic design is planned to enhance the understanding and memorability of messages derived from complex scientific information and data. Infographics and data-visualisation are effective tools that combine aesthetic appeal with simplicity, helping to translate complex messages for specific target audiences. Infographics can facilitate understanding of project activities and are particularly useful for raising awareness to the partnership, specifically through social media. Data visualisation supports the communication of complex data in an intuitive and accessible way. To better convey the messages of PARC partnership we will use a range of visual communication tools across different channels, including scientific illustrations, infographics, conceptual diagrams, maps, tables and figures, animations and video clips.

A wide range of communication products will be developed over the course of the PARC partnership, as follows.

8.1. PARC visual identity

A PARC visual identity was created before December 2022. This included a logo package; of palette of colours; templates for presentations, reports, deliverables, and letters; an e-mail signature; an event agenda; a graphic-roll-out, and a design concept for data visualisation (figures and graphs). It also featured a [leaflet](#) translated into 22 languages, templates for the PARC Sampler and the PARC Science Digest as well as several interactive media design and animated communication products.

To ensure a consistent visual and graphical language for all dissemination products, a PARC Visual Identity and Branding Manual was drafted and shared with all partners. A PARC alphabet also was created. All materials are available on the PARC website under the [Media](#) section.

The branding identity of PARC forms a core communication tool, ensuring consistency and recognisability across all outputs. By applying the branding identity systematically across publications, websites, social media, presentations, and events, PARC strengthens its visibility and credibility while making its communication more accessible and recognisable to stakeholders.

8.2. The PARC website

The PARC website (www.eu-parc.eu) having been serves as the main showcase for the project, providing a comprehensive overview since its launch in December 2022. All partners are encouraged to contribute with content to the website. The working language of the website is English. There are no internal pages, as the ANSES SharePoint is used for storing internal documents.

Since its launch, the PARC website has been consistently enriched and expanded to reflect the evolving scope of the partnership's activities and engagement efforts. Each year, new sections are created, new content is added, and existing sections are updated to ensure the platform remains relevant, informative, and user-friendly for all target audiences. This ongoing development allows the website to serve as a dynamic hub for internal communication, external visibility, and strategic stakeholder engagement.

8.3. Newsletters

Two types of newsletters are foreseen to be sent out.

8.3.1. PARC Sampler

An electronic newsletter with the highlights and updates about the partnership's activities and tasks as well as results, deliverables, events, etc. TA subscription option to the newsletter is available and as of June 2025, the newsletter has a total of 1,248 subscribers.

The HubSpot contact management system, managed by the European Environment Agency, provides a dynamic contact database for distributing the newsletter. It allows stakeholders to register (and unregister) electronically to receive communications by email. The application provides an easy way for users to send email newsletters, manage (and categorise) subscriber lists, and track campaign performance. In line with GDPR regulations, individuals must actively subscribe to the newsletter themselves, as it is not possible to add subscribers.

All partners are expected to contribute with content to the newsletter. The internal procedure for drafting and approving content of the newsletter is outlined in the PARC Handbook. The biannual newsletter is accessible via the PARC website and is also distributed through electronic channels such as social media. As of the end of June 2025, five issues have been published

8.3.2. PARC Science Digest

To increase the visibility of the many peer-reviewed publications that PARC produces amongst the different target audiences, but also to make their outcome digestible to non-scientific audiences, clear and concise key messages are sent in an attractive format to make it easier to capture their importance. For that purpose, the PARC Science Digest is designed and sent out monthly. Like the PARC Sampler, individuals need to subscribe to the newsletter to receive it.

Once a peer reviewed publication is published, the corresponding author submits key research and regulatory messages to be used for the dissemination of the publication's outcome. Scientific publications and their key messages are further disseminated in social media. In total, 17 issues have been published by the end of June 2025.

8.4. Policy briefs

Policy briefs are a tool that gives concise, objective summaries of relevant scientific information, as well as recommendations tailored for policymakers. They serve as a vehicle for providing evidence-based policy advice to help policymakers make informed decisions. These documents are particularly valuable for high-level decision-makers, such as members of the Governing Board who have very limited time to review extensive materials. The timing of policy brief publication should be strategically aligned with key decision-making processes and meetings of expert groups and committees.

In addition, the EU Hub will be consulted to gather feedback on the current list of proposed policy brief topics. This outreach aims to identify stakeholder priorities and determine which briefs are considered most relevant or urgent from a policy perspective. Such consultation helps ensure alignment with both stakeholder needs and evolving EU policy agendas.

As of June 2025, two policy briefs have been officially confirmed: one on Non-Targeted Screening (NTS) and another on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD). A third brief, focused on chemicals and biodiversity, is currently under development.

8.5. Videos

Videos can serve as simple, low-information “teasers” designed to spark curiosity and guide users toward more detailed information. Videos can fulfil different purposes depending on the audience: while members of the general public can stop on the first “step” of the exploration process, journalists and scientists may choose to explore more in-depth content and information. We are considering the development of several promotional videos. A concept note is currently being drafted to propose the creation of such videos, for instance, one-to-one interviews with PARC researchers to explain their work and provide context for their achieved results.

A series of videos was recorded during the PARC consortium meeting held in Tirol (Austria) in May 2024. The videos were first published on the European Environment Agency (EEA) YouTube channel and subsequently shared bi-weekly on PARC social media channels: Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram and X. The video campaign on social media ran from August 2024 to February 2025, featured a total of 13 videos. The videos showcased PARC leaders, experts and partners, highlighting the broad range of activities carried out within the partnership. Each post included a summary of the video content, links to experts’ and institutions’ profiles, links to related PARC activities and targeted hashtags emphasising key aspects of the content. The campaign was designed to act as a “hook”, driving traffic to the PARC website for more in-depth information. Among the platforms used, LinkedIn proved to be the most effective, generating the highest levels of audience engagement, including likes, comments, and reposts.

Overall, the video campaign demonstrated that short, stakeholder-driven videos are an effective communication tool for engaging both the general public and scientific audiences, as reflected in the diverse user profiles interacting with the posts. An example of one such video can be found [here](#).

8.6. Scientific publications

Scientific publications are primarily aimed at informing the academic community. PARC promotes these publications through a strong open access policy. Guidelines concerning content, referencing and notification procedures are outlined in PARC's Handbook (under the section ‘Communication and dissemination of results and open access requirements’) which all partners are required to follow. Scientific publications are listed on the PARC website, as well as disseminated on the Science Digest Newsletter

and social media and previously uploaded on the PARC community on Zenodo. As of June 2025, more than 130 scientific publications have been uploaded on the PARC website, on the Science Digest Newsletter and social media and previously uploaded on the PARC community on Zenodo.

8.7. Technical reports/deliverables

Research results are summarised in concise and targeted technical reports and deliverables. Efforts are made to ensure that key audiences receive these documents with follow-up provided as needed to offer additional clarification. All deliverables are available [here](#).

8.8. Exhibitions

The PARC exhibition "Healthy Horizons: Our Journey to Create a Safer Chemical World" was launched during the PARC Consortium meeting, held from 13 to 16 May 2024 in Hall in Tirol, Austria. This exhibition showcased PARC ongoing efforts and collaborative initiatives aimed at fostering a safer and healthier environment through innovative chemical risk assessment research and regulation. The exhibition featured engaging visual displays, videos, and interactive elements explaining how science informs policy. Read further details [here](#). Considering the success of this initiative, another exhibition is foreseen for the PARC final meeting.

8.9. Mini surveys

Mini surveys have been developed and will soon be implemented on the PARC website as a tool to better understand audience opinions and gather quick insights. They also serve to increase user engagement. Each mini survey will consist of questions with answer options such as yes/no. These surveys can be strategically placed throughout the website, in sections such as news items, research project pages, and other relevant content areas, to encourage interaction and collect targeted feedback. The mini surveys will be promoted through social media and email channels. See example [here](#).

8.10. News and events

In order to increase PARC visibility, the PARC website includes dedicated sections on "[News](#)" and "[Events](#)", tailored to different target audiences, with clear and concise messages.

Within the Events sub-section, content is organised by event type, including: 1) trainings; 2) workshops; 3) international conferences; 4) national events; 5) PARC internal meetings; and 6) other events. Each announcement includes key highlights, practical details and information about the event and PARC's involvement or contributions. A clear internal procedure was established for the selection of published events, based on dissemination proposals submitted by PARC partners.

Under the News sub-section, content was divided into 9 thematic categories: 1) Risk assessment; 2) Tools and resources; 3) Building capacities; 4) Science to policy; 5) Scientific publications; 6) Results; 7) What's on; 8) National hubs; and 9) General. As previously mentioned, this section is currently being updated with news resulting from suggestions collected during the regular Management Board (MB) meetings.

As of the end of July 2025, the PARC website featured a total of 117 events and 124 news items, reflecting Task 3.2 commitment to ensuring timely and relevant dissemination of information to a wide range of stakeholders.

9. Proposal for new communication products for 2025-2029

In February 2025, Task 3.2 presented a proposal for new communication products to the Management Board during its meeting in Copenhagen. The aim is to enhance the visibility, accessibility, and impact of PARC research by introducing a refreshed suite of communication tools, tailored to different audiences and aligned with strategic policy windows.

These products are designed to go beyond traditional reporting and promote more engaging, inclusive, and interactive forms of dissemination. Key proposals include policy cards and an interactive dashboard, enabling policymakers and regulators to filter and explore research messages relevant to specific themes or regulatory priorities. To enhance storytelling, a series of impact stories and a “Chemical Chronicles” podcast were proposed as means to communicate the real-world relevance of PARC findings.

Data visualisation tools, such as interactive maps and publication content clouds, can help users draw connections across studies and topics. Infographics and short videos will make content more accessible for citizens and media audiences. A final printed magazine or digital publication will curate the most significant scientific and societal insights from across the partnership.

To broaden public outreach, a citizen awareness campaign was recommended, including social media activations, fact sheets, and collaborations with influencers or science communicators. A PARC Art-Science Award was also proposed to promote creative interpretations of scientific research and encourage interdisciplinary dialogue. Finally, a closing exhibition at the European Parliament would serve as a high-profile opportunity to showcase PARC’s key achievements and impact.

All proposed products will be developed with sustainability and long-term usability in mind, ensuring they continue to inform, inspire, and engage audiences beyond the project’s lifetime.

10. How to make full use of the results?

As part of dissemination and exploitation activities, PARC outputs have been and will be presented at scientific conferences, workshops and events. These events provide valuable opportunities for dialogue and communication with a diverse range of potential end users, networking and increase the visibility of the PARC brand. Events attended by PARC partners are reported to the WP3 co-leaders and published on the PARC website to support further dissemination by partners.

PARC partners are expected to actively participate in major international conferences and symposia and act as ambassadors for the project. Additionally, our results will be communicated at conferences organised at national level, leveraging the multilingual capabilities of our multi-cultural team and fostering synergies among different partners. We will also explore opportunities to organise side events at international negotiation fora relevant to chemicals management and public health more generally.

At the same time, PARC will specifically target events and organise its own activities, including workshops, discussion forums, face to face meetings. These will serve to communicate and exchange knowledge, to maintain meaningful collaborations and cooperation and facilitate focused discussions on specific topics, with specific groups such as policymakers, risk assessors and managers, industry representatives and

NGOs. This targeted and strategic approach will help maximise the impact of PARC's outcomes. Furthermore, these events will create a space to identify and prioritise joint challenges, develop strategic research and innovation agendas in collaboration with the scientific community and ensure that results are applied within a regulatory context, thereby fostering trust and confidence.

Bringing together policymakers and researchers, key stakeholders, workers associations, NGOs and industry through conferences, seminars, and workshops is an effective way for researchers and scientists to communicate their work. These events will showcase the scientific achievements of PARC, while also providing valuable opportunities for sharing knowledge, networking and raising awareness of the PARC partnership.

Partner institutions regularly publish news and updates on their websites and social media channels. These platforms will also be used to consistently disseminate information about PARC's activities and progress.

It is now widely recognised that improving access to research results enhances both the quality and efficiency of science and drives innovation i across public and private sectors. In this context, and to support the dissemination and reuse of scientific results, we will:

- Use initiatives such as the Open Research Europe and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), facilitated by the European Commission, to submit research publications. EOSC also plays a key role in the European Data Strategy, which aims to position the EU as a global leader in a data-driven society.
- Ensure regular updates to the CORDIS website managed by the Coordination Team. This platform can be used by the European Commission to develop editorial products that increase visibility of PARC's results to potential partners.
- Use the Horizon Results Platform (HRP), a matchmaking tool that enables us to publish and promote our Key Exploitable Results vis-à-vis our targeted audiences – stakeholders, policy makers, potential business partners, etc. The HRP also allows beneficiaries to manage their result profiles and update them as needed.

11. Engagement with key stakeholders

11.1. Engagement with the PARC Governing Board

The Governing Board (GB) is the overarching body of PARC, providing the highest-level strategic guidance for the Partnership. It plays a key role in securing political commitment for the uptake of PARC's results and ensuring its long-term sustainability. The GB includes representatives from the relevant Ministries of all participating countries, as well as key Directorates-General (DGs) of the European Commission.

Specific communication material for PARC GB members could be designed and produced. While these materials may share similarities with content developed for high level decision-makers and policymakers—due to overlapping interests—, further tailoring to the specific role and needs of the GB would enhance their effectiveness and relevance.

In addition to the communication channels established within PARC, Governing Board members were informed about recent developments on the PARC website during their meeting on 14 November 2023.

Many Governing Board members also attended the interactive event “Healthy Horizons: Our Journey to Create a Safer Chemical World,” held in Hall in Tirol, Austria in 2024, demonstrating their continued engagement with the Partnership.

Looking ahead, further activities are planned to increase awareness and encourage usage of existing communication tools, such as providing a dedicated presentation that outlines recent updates to the PARC website and highlights key developments.

11.2. Engagement with the National Hubs

At the national level, the National Hubs (NHs) play a crucial role in disseminating PARC results and raising public awareness.

To address country-specific needs, the communication priorities of the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) are collected annually through Task 2.3. These priorities are reviewed in close consultation with NHCPs, and additional meetings with the National Hub Co-Coordinator are planned to further refine the process and ensure responsiveness to evolving national contexts.

As a practical example, a general PARC information leaflet — intended for national use — was developed in 22 languages, in collaboration with the NHCPs. In addition, a range of communication templates has been produced to support national outreach efforts, including presentation slides, roll-ups, posters, and video production guidelines. Task 3.2 will continue to develop and propose specific communication products tailored to the specific needs of the NH.

In 2023, Task 3.2 organised a workshop and training session for the National Hubs focused on enhancing the impact of communication activities at the national level. To further support visibility and engagement, a dedicated “National hubs” news category was launched on the PARC website, where several national success stories have since been featured and promoted via the PARC Sampler newsletter.

In addition, Task 3.2 launched a webinar series on risk communication, open to all stakeholders, including National Hub members. The series aims to build capacity for effectively communicating the health risks of chemicals, both within the PARC community and to broader audiences. Task 3.2 is continuously in contact with NH Coordinators in order to identify their specific needs for communication and dissemination and to inform them on how NH can support PARC to disseminate communication materials, e.g., surveys at National level.

11.3. Engagement with the Stakeholder Forum

Building on the experience gained from HBM4EU, the PARC Stakeholder Forum (SF) is composed of 15 organisations focusing on risk assessment of chemicals, risk communication, science-to-public and/or science-to-policy interactions. They represent different parts of society in order to bring the opportunity for a combined, cross-sectoral chemical risk assessment, covering production, provision, use and potential impact of chemicals in society, as well as the production and use of knowledge.

Engagement with the SF is an integral part of PARC’s broader engagement strategy. The members of the SF are expected to contribute with feedback and input, to maximise the benefits and impact of PARC results, both for achieving PARC objectives as well as for their own activities with similar objectives.

SF interacts with the PARC consortium. Other exchanges have been possible as well through ad hoc (online) meetings and consultations. Task 3.2 has delivered presentations at multiple SF meetings, contributing to ongoing dialogue and increasing the Forum’s visibility. In addition, interviews with Forum members are being featured as part of the news section on the PARC website, highlighting the diverse perspectives and contributions of stakeholders involved in the Partnership. A series of interviews is planned, with some already conducted during the consortium meeting in Tirol, where two SF members

shared their insights. These efforts further demonstrate the active engagement of the Stakeholder Forum in PARC and reinforce its role in promoting inclusive and transparent communication.

11.4. Engagement with citizens

Citizens' engagement should involve not only a strong understanding of chemical exposure but also efforts to build trust in risk assessment and management. With this purpose in mind, targeted actions include not only information campaigns but also accessible, practical, and context-specific actions that address citizens' real-life decision-making processes. These can include, for example, activities that enhance general literacy levels and demystify product labels to counter misleading marketing. Involving citizens in the co-design of communication strategies is pivotal for empowering informed choices and bridging the gap between technical knowledge and public perception in the context of everyday chemical exposures.

To foster citizens' engagement in PARC, several activities are being conducted in partner countries, namely, focus groups and citizen surveys. Focus groups are a qualitative research method that enables structured group discussions, encouraging participants to share and clarify their views and ideas. The primary aim is to gather more in-depth information about citizens' needs, perceptions, and concerns regarding chemicals and other related topics, and to develop targeted communication materials that effectively address these issues.

A total of 20 countries is expected to host focus groups (two per partner; four countries per year), involving adults aged 18 and over with diverse backgrounds - including variations in gender, education level, living environment, professional activity, and parental status. The aim is to ensure representation from different regions across Europe, encompassing both large and small countries, where citizens may hold differing perceptions of chemical safety.

To ensure methodological consistency across all participating countries and allow for comparability of results, each research team undergoes training prior to conducting the focus groups. The first training session focuses on the fundamental aspects of organising focus groups and preparing the data. This includes principles of qualitative research, sampling, developing the discussion guide, managing group dynamics, and transcription guidelines. A second training session addresses the content analysis of the collected data.

To date, eight focus groups (two per country) have been conducted in Finland, Latvia, Portugal, and Sweden, with a total of 62 citizens taking part.

Key topics emerging across all discussions included: sources of exposure; perspectives on chemical use - both benefits and concerns; access to information and levels of literacy; health consequences of chemical exposure; contexts and factors that increase exposure risk; vulnerable population groups; pathways and routes of exposure; individual protection measures; and regulatory and management strategies.

Another approach being used to characterise citizens' perspectives and concerns about chemicals in daily used products is the citizen survey. This will be repeated at the end of the project which will be used to monitor the effects of PARC activities outcomes and to support future activities after PARC.

Different communication tools (e.g. factsheets, short videos, etc.) are planned to be developed in PARC to increase the engagement of the European citizens.

11.5. Other activities to engage stakeholders

Task 3.2 has actively engaged with various work packages by delivering tailored presentations during their meetings, helping to ensure alignment and visibility of communication and stakeholder engagement efforts. In parallel, regular updates have been shared with the entire PARC consortium to summarise

recent achievements and available tools. These updates aim to strengthen internal communication, raise awareness of existing resources, and encourage their broader use. As part of the ongoing communication strategy, additional stakeholder engagement activities are also being explored to further expand outreach beyond the consortium.

12. Social media strategy

Social media continues to serve as an important channel for disseminating results and promoting engagement with PARC. At the same time, the ever-changing nature of social media platforms — characterized by concise and fast-paced content — poses challenges to the communication of complex scientific knowledge. Nevertheless, PARC has successfully leveraged these platforms to build awareness, stimulate dialogue, and inform both stakeholders and the public.

Social media presents opportunities to:

- promote PARC brand and establish a strong reputation,
- inspire stakeholders and the public to engage in dialogue,
- raise awareness of project activities and outcomes,
- disseminate updates on studies, surveys, workshops, and news related to project results, actions, and events,
- enhance the recruitment of participants for surveys and other project-related activities.

In line with the overall communication strategy, the social media strategy - initially drafted in early 2023 - has been progressively implemented and refined. It aims to strengthen PARC's visibility, foster public engagement, and support recruitment and outreach goals through targeted and effective use of digital tools.

This strategy leverages:

- **New formats:** Social media channels allow for tailored content aligned with the preferences of diverse user groups. The approach prioritises the use of different post formats tailored to each platform and audience to optimize engagement.
- **New, relevant content:** Communicating complex scientific findings in accessible ways to a broader audience remains a challenge. The updated approach aims to test simplified but meaningful content that resonates with both expert and general audiences.
- **New voices:** Beyond institutional messaging, the strategy highlights the people behind PARC. Partners are encouraged to share their work and perspectives, adding authenticity and a human element to the communication.

Progress highlights:

Platform-specific content: content is customised for major platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and X, with a focus on visual consistency, clarity, and audience engagement.

- **Editorial coordination:** a flexible editorial calendar to coordinate communication across partners and thematic areas, while allowing for the timely dissemination of project outcomes, publications, and events.

- Targeted campaigns: specific targeted campaigns—such as those for HBM studies or thematic content— have been developed and promoted, including paid promotional efforts to maximise the strong organic social media performance already achieved. Governance and quality control: a multi-level governance model for content creation and quality assurance, involving coordination, content, and editorial teams.
- Performance tracking: Platform-native analytics tools are used to monitor reach, engagement, and growth.

A social media editorial calendar is regularly populated based on input from the WPs. Task 2.3 partners, responsible for developing and managing the project's social media presence, use the calendar to plan monthly posts.

Two examples of social media campaigns are presented below:

1. Human biomonitoring (HBM) campaign

The HBM studies aim to generate comparable and harmonised data on chemical exposure in the general population across EU countries, with a focus on children, teenagers, and adults aged 6 to 39 years. The initiative supports the identification of exposure sources and determinants, characterises exposure to chemical mixtures, and assesses potential health effects by aligning national and regional HBM programmes.

A targeted social media campaign was launched to disseminate key findings from the HBM studies to a broader audience. Developed in close collaboration with study partners and communication teams, the campaign was launched on 10 July 2024 and provides regular updates on study progress and milestones via PARC's social media channels.

Campaign activities included:

- development and dissemination of content across all PARC social media platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram and X) creation of tailored messages and custom visuals by including quotes from principal investigators (and survey participants)
- tagging of relevant organisations, institutions, and individual partners.

This campaign promoted transparency and public engagement throughout the study by keeping audiences informed about key milestones. The overarching goal was to ensure broad and effective communication of the HBM study results, increasing public awareness and fostering stakeholder engagement across Europe.

The progress and strategy of the campaign were structured as follows:

- Key message development: Based on partner feedback and presentations, key messages were crafted to highlight scientific and societal relevance.
- Content alignment: Posts were designed in line with PARC's tone and style, emphasizing the social impact of the HBM studies and highlighting the different global milestones.
- Visual engagement: Posts included images and/or custom-designed visuals to reinforce key messages and encourage user interaction.
- Network amplification: A curated list of PARC partners' social media accounts enabled tagging, increased mutual engagement and created opportunities for cross-promotion.

- Stakeholder engagement: quotes and other inputs were asked from research owners. These contributions strengthened authenticity, visibility and stakeholder engagement.

2. Research projects campaign

To enhance the visibility of PARC's research projects and increase traffic to the website, a content strategy was developed for promotion via social media. This campaign was aligned with the broader initiative to update the research project section of the PARC website, ensuring that each project is represented with relevant, engaging and accessible content.

The campaign included the following key activities:

1. A standardised template was developed to guide both the composition and visual representation of content for each research project (Figure 4). This ensured coherence across posts and helped communication teams—especially given the rotating social media editorial team every two months—maintain a consistent style and tone.
2. The template provided clear guidelines on both content writing and visual representation of each research project.
3. The campaign was integrated into the social media calendar from February 2025 onwards, with a fixed weekly posting schedule. Every Wednesday, a new research project was introduced, often linked to trending topics or international awareness day. To date, more than 20 projects have been featured, with additional ones planned throughout 2025.
4. Special attention was given to highlighting the partners involved in each project. A tagging strategy—primarily focused on LinkedIn, where tagging is most effective—was implemented to ensure partner visibility and encourage interaction.
5. A mapping of partners' presence on LinkedIn was carried out to support accurate and consistent tagging.

Research projects have proven to be among the most engaging content on PARC's social media channels. They consistently perform well in terms of average interactions per post and receive a high volume of quality comments, reflecting genuine interest from the audience.

This campaign has proven to be an effective tool for increasing the visibility of PARC's expertise, strengthening partner engagement and fostering open, constructive dialogue with the online community.

Figure 4. An example of social media post and the related editorial tips.

PARC
Publicado por Filipa Primo
- 21 h · 🌐

📌 Project - Assessing chemical exposure in infants: smarter tools for vulnerable populations

Infants are especially vulnerable to harmful chemicals due to their developing organs, rapid growth, and unique exposure patterns. Yet today, most exposure assessments are based on adult models, missing the nuance needed to protect our youngest population.

🔍 Which challenges are addressed in this work?

- ✔ Limited understanding of infant-specific exposure pathways
- ✔ Inadequate data on combined chemical exposures
- ✔ Lack of tailored risk assessment tools for early life stages

📌 What is PARC doing?

- ✔ Developing innovative tools and methods to assess chemical exposure in infants more accurately
- ✔ Evaluating multiple exposure routes—including air, dust, food contact materials, and mouthing behavior—using real-world data
- ✔ Improving early-life risk assessments to support protective policies and safety standards tailored to infants

With this PARC project it will be possible to enhance the accuracy and relevance of chemical exposure assessments for infants, ultimately contributing to improved public health protection strategies.

🔗 Learn more about this project: <https://www.eu-parc.eu/.../developing-and-testing-new...>

Partners involved in the project: AU (DK), AUTH (GR), BPI (GR), CEA (FR), CSIC (ES), EHESP (FR), INRAE (FR), ISCI (ES), IISPV (ES), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), KUM (DE), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), SU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UGR (ES), UNIABDN (GB), UniLU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), VUA (NL), WR (NL), LNS (LU)

#EU_PARC #InfantHealth #ChemicalExposure #RiskAssessment #VulnerablePopulations #ChildSafety

PARC PROJECTS

Editorial tips

Title - select a representative emoji and sentence about the core topic of the project. Try not to use caps letters, only at the beginning of the sentence.

1st paragraph - highlight the importance of the project to people's lives, using catching questions or strong commitment sentences with the project's objectives

1st bullet points: Questions to answer with this research

2nd bullet points: deliverables of the project

Last paragraph: summary of the overall results that can be assured by the project as well as its correlation with PARC's scope of work. Try to keep it as simple as a sentence.

Relevant links: use as much information as you feel relevant to the topic, driving people to the website. Include the research webpage as well as other scientific publication or project that is related to the topic. Up to 2 links suggested.

List of partners involved in the project: in Unkedin tag the institutions and in Facebook and Instagram use the list presented in the research webpage.

Hashtags: always include #EU_PARC in the list and select other key concepts that are relevant to the project. Don't use more than 8 hashtags.

Image: select humanized images with people or spaces relatable to the project's topic. Avoid IA images. Select photos from AdobeStock when possible. Always include in Figma "PARC Projects" reference.

general tip: revise all content considering british english

13. Media strategy

Both specialised and mainstream media offer a gateway to the public, stakeholders and policy makers, allowing access to new audiences and multiplying messages. Our media approach will range from electronic to printed media, targeting both news and feature pieces alike.

At the same time, chemical risk is a complex and sensitive topic, and these factors affect the modalities of communicating with broader audiences. It is important to balance the responsibility to communicate evidence of negative health impacts with the potential drawbacks of raising public concern, in particular when the possibility for change is limited. We will also need to decide when evidence is sufficiently robust to be shared, how to clearly communicate any uncertainties, and how to reflect diverse opinions on the interpretation of the evidence.

Ideally, an extensive database of regional, national and international media contacts should be developed, to announce key events and results. The European Environment Agency has a core network of journalists around Europe, and through the institution, it is possible to channel media-oriented news and updates. In

addition, we will collaborate with the National Hubs to identify target media outlets in each partner country. All project partners are encouraged to contribute to media exposure at a regional and national level through their institutional PR departments.

Actions to secure media coverage will include producing press releases and contributing to editorials, as well as providing targeted materials and/or participating in interviews.

The Coordinator Team has served as the primary contact for interested stakeholders, but WP3 is responsible for handling interview requests. Each request will be assessed to determine the most appropriate consortium member to conduct the interview, especially when specialised expertise is required.

A media kit will be developed and uploaded on the PARC website. A concise press and PR strategy, outlining targets, activities and a work plan will be drafted in 2026. This strategy will be aligned with the social media strategy and the overall communication strategy.

Content includes the following:

- Press clippings
- Activities to liaise with communication departments of partner institutions to ensure a broad media coverage whenever possible (including on-line briefing events with journalists)
- Media Kit
- Stories to pitch to the media towards the end of the project
- List of magazines and non-specialised media outlets (i.e. Horizon magazine, Research EU magazines, etc.), journalists (media database), bloggers and influencers, including national media in each partner country and National Hubs

14. Communication work plan

The communication plan is a dynamic document that is not fixed but is updated throughout the year. Additional products, events and activities will be added, as the project develops.

Every two years, Task 3.2 conducts a mapping exercise to identify upcoming results and deliverables across PARC that can be translated into communication and outreach activities. This will help ensure timely, targeted promotion of key outputs and better alignment with stakeholder needs and policy opportunities.

Work package leads are asked to provide:

- A brief description of upcoming results or deliverables (including planned publications),
- The expected timeline and release date, if known,
- A short note on the type of knowledge created.

This exercise supports strategic communication planning and enhances the visibility and impact of PARC's scientific work.

Each year, a new set of communication products is developed to disseminate the knowledge generated.

15. Risk communication

The risk communication strategy aims to widely disseminate the new knowledge produced in PARC ensuring its “evergreen potential” while protecting it from misinformation and disinformation. This valuable knowledge primarily includes information on the risks posed by specific chemicals and scientific evidence necessary for effective risk management decision making.

Risk communication within PARC can be seen as the interactive exchange of information and opinions among partners and the end users regarding risk analysis research results on chemical hazards and risks, risk-related factors and risk perceptions.

The risk communication strategy is dynamic requiring ongoing input about the nature and source of each chemical hazard in relation to risk, who or what is affected and to what extent, the degree of exposure and the capacity of individuals or public authorities to manage the risk.

PARC partners must engage in dialogue with the end users of the project's results, including policymakers and other stakeholders. Clear, straightforward, simplified messages need to be developed to raise public awareness, facilitate public participation in the broader debate on chemicals and inform people about chemical safety.

The risk perception of all interested parties must be considered to facilitate mutual understanding and dialogue. The valuable new knowledge produced in the project should be presented clearly and accessibly— including to individuals not directly involved in the process or laypersons not having a scientific background — while duly respecting applicable legal provisions on confidentiality and protection of personal data.

Understanding information about chemicals from various sources (such as soil, wastewater, products, and food), as well as associated risks and safety is often an unconscious, cognitive process influenced by motivational and emotional factors. Risk perception encompasses beliefs, attitudes, judgments, and feelings; it is shaped by opinions and influenced by many factors beyond statistical risk assessments. These include cognitive factors, emotional factors, socio-cultural factors and individual differences,

demographics, personality dispositions and traits, past-experience, perceived benefit, heuristics among others.

Understanding cognitive and decision-making processes is critical for overcoming biases and the mental or conceptual frameworks people use to evaluate and interpret risk. This is essential for developing strategies that are appropriately targeted and effectively formulated.

It is important to remember that perceived risk is inherently subjective. Since risk cannot be measured independently of people's perceptions and cultural contexts, the concept of "real" or "objective" risk is of limited practical use. This suggests a need for segmentation of audiences and for moving away from a one-size-fits-all approach (tailoring communication for different groups such as stakeholders, general public, experts, academic community etc.).

In relation to the expected outcomes of the PARC project the basic rules and guidelines of risk communication are as follows:

- Scientific evidence is the basis of risk communication.
- Maintain the integrity of information.
- Be clear, consistent and transparent.
- Consider your purpose and tailor messages to audience's needs and expectations.
- Choose the most appropriate communication tools and channels, depending on the PARC consortium's objectives and the intended target audiences (e.g., based on Eurobarometer findings or dedicated surveys).
- Ensure timely communication about the latest news and findings from the project.
- Use innovative tools to capture attention, especially when addressing non-specialist audiences.
- Avoid overloading a single communication tool with excessive or mixed information— focus on delivering one key message per communication tool, namely "one chemical risk – one message"
- Carefully design campaigns (if used), to combine communication tools and channels in a way that increases outreach and strengthens engagement
- When information is incomplete, clearly state any uncertainties.
- Set KPIs to fine-tune the strategy.

PARC's risk communication activities also aim to enhance skills of risk communicators. In 2024, EFET and NIJZ conducted a pilot study in Greece and Slovenia to assess the current landscape of risk communication, taking also cultural differences into account. A validated survey was conducted among experienced risk communicators, focusing on their perceptions of their roles, their approaches to risk communicators, the tools they use and how they use language to communicate risk from chemicals.

Key findings from the study suggest that:

- Risk communicators recognise the importance of training, although a small percentage (13 %) have never received any kind of training in risk communication.
- The main challenges faced by risk communicators, ranked by priority are as follow: unclear role distribution, lack of adequate scientific data, lack of measurement systems and—specifically in Greece—budget constraints.
- Risk communicators place nearly equal importance on the audience's trust in themselves (the messengers), their institutions and the message itself.
- While risk communicators acknowledge the inherent uncertainty involved in risk communication, many also believe that emphasizing uncertainty can confuse the public.
- Risk communicators are aware that biases, heuristics and their own personal choices influence the way they convey risk-related information.
- Experts need to further familiarise themselves with using social media, as integrating both traditional and social media is necessary for robust and effective communication.

- The majority of respondents reported addressing misinformation by issuing statements containing correct information, while a smaller portion (10 %) reported taking no action.
- Although most respondents recognise the importance of using appropriate language in their messaging, a significant proportion still selected messages with distorted or incomplete information when asked to choose between three options, two of which were intentionally inaccurate or incomplete.

The study identified several training needs for risk communicators, including strengthening expertise, building networks, fostering trust, addressing uncertainty, effectively using social media and tailoring language to different audiences. A validated questionnaire will be distributed across all PARC countries to gain broader insights. To address the identified needs, PARC launched a webinar series on risk communication, with approximately three sessions held annually. The second webinar, held on 26 March 2025, presented results from the surveys conducted in Greece and Slovenia. Future webinars will continue to explore key aspects of risk communication.

16. Monitoring and evaluation

Key indicators have been identified for PARC communication activities to measure the success of our efforts and outputs. The impact indicator framework identified under Task 1.3 will be used, ensuring that communication metrics align with the overall approach established in Task 1.3. The evaluation will take place on a biannual basis.

See below the key indicators identified, which will be linked with the performance indicators defined under Tasks 1.3.

Table 4. Metrics to be measured.

Activity	Metric	Explanation
PARC website	Unique visitors	The number of unique users requesting pages from the website during a given period, regardless of how often they visit
	Visits	The number of visits (or sessions) to the website
	Page views	Number of pages requested (also called Page Impressions)
	Return Visit Rate	The Return Visit Rate is calculated by dividing the number of visits from returning visitors by the total number of visits to the site. A high Return Visit Rate indicates strong visitor loyalty
	Time spent per visit	The average amount of time spent per visit. It can serve as an indicator of interest.
	Page views per visit	The average number of pages viewed per visit. It can serve as an indicator of interest.
	Bounce rate	Bounce rate is defined as the percentage of visits in which only one page is viewed before the visitor exits. A high bounce rate suggests that the content of the page may not be relevant to the user or that the user cannot find the information they need quickly enough.
	Conversation rate or goal completion rate	The percentage of visitors who complete a defined goal, such as signing up for a newsletter or downloading a PDF.
	Other information useful to know	Geographic location Traffic sources (referrals) help understand where users are coming from: direct (typing the URL), referral (following a link from another webpage), paid (banner or other ad), and social (links from social platforms).

Facebook	Page likes	Total (accumulated) page likes
	Impressions	Posts views count.
	Reach (total)	Number of users that have been exposed to a page post (item) or any item related to the page.
	Engagement rate	The percentage of people who liked, commented on, shared or clicked a post after being exposed to it
	Posts (number)	Number of posts published in the profile
	Reach	Number of users exposed to the post
	Interactions	Total number of reactions, comments, shares, and clicks per post
	Reactions	Total number of reactions (like, celebrate, support, funny, love, interesting, curious) on the posts
	Shares	Total number of times the posts have been shared
	Comments	Total number of comments on a post
	Clicks	Total number of times people clicked on the post (including links, follow button, photos, mentions, or others)
YouTube	Views (total)	Accumulated views for all videos posted under PARC
	Views (per post)	Accumulated views per video posted under PARC
	Likes (total)	Total likes on all videos posted under PARC
	Likes (per post)	Accumulated likes per video posted under PARC
Instagram	Followers	Number of Instagram users following your account
	Impressions	Number of times the posts have been viewed
	Reach (total)	Number of users exposed to the page
	Engagement rate	Percentage of people who liked, commented, shared or clicked a post after being exposed to it
	Posts	Number of posts published on the profile
	Reach	Number of users exposed to the post
	Interactions	Total number of reactions, comments, shares, and clicks per post
	Likes	Total number of reactions (like, celebrate, support, funny, love, interesting, curious) on the posts
	Shares	Total number of times the posts have been shared
	Comments	Total number of comments on a post
X	Followers	Number of X users following the account
	Post	Number of posts published on the profile
	Impressions	Number of times the posts have been viewed
	Engagement (Rate)	Any actions (including retweets and favourites) taken on a tweet, divided by the number of impressions the tweet received
	Replies	Comments on a post
	Retweets	Total number of times tweets has been retweeted by other users
LinkedIn	Followers	Number of profiles who follow the page

	Visitors	Number of unique visitors to the page
	Posts/content	Number of posts published on the page
	Impressions (total/ organic)	How many times the posts have been viewed
	Average impressions per post	Average of number of times a post has been viewed
	Engagement (Rate)	Number of times users interacted with your post divided by the number of impressions the post received
	Interactions (total)	Total number of reactions, comments, shares, and clicks per post
	Reactions	Total number of reactions (like, celebrate, support, funny, love, interesting, curious) on the posts
	Shares	Total number of times the posts have been shared
	Comments	Total number of comments on a post
	Clicks	Total number of times people clicked on the post (whether on links, follow button, photos, mentions, or others)
PARC newsletters	Subscribers	Number of people subscribed to the newsletter
	Unsubscribes	Number of people unsubscribing from the newsletter (An increased number of unsubscribers after a publication is an indicator of dissatisfaction with the newsletter)
	Open rate	Percentage of subscribers who open the newsletter
	Forward rate	Percentage of subscribers who forward the newsletter to friends or colleagues
	Bound rate	Percentage of mails not delivered due to closed email accounts, error in email address (Quality in subscribers' list)
	Click rate	Percentage of clicks on at least one link within the newsletter
	Conversation rate	Percentage of subscribers who perform the desired action. This includes the number of visits and unique visitors. The most and least popular interest (most visited) and those of low interest as well as the time spent reading.
Events (conferences, workshops, webinars, PR events)	Attendance	Attendance numbers from EU and national authorities, industry and NGOs, if available.
	Number of collaborations	Number of potential collaborations generated by the event
	Evaluation form	Comments and scores from the evaluation form
	Number of presentations given	Number of presentations given at a conference
Reports	Open rate	Percentage of users who open the publication from the email
	Forward rate	Percentage of subscribers who forward the publication to friends/ or colleagues
	Bounce rate	Percentage of mails not delivered due to closed email accounts, error in mail address or similar issues
Peer reviewed publications	Number of publications	Number of scientific publications produced in PARC (to be discussed and approved by Task 3.1)
	Sum of the impact factor	All peer reviewed PARC publications are considered.
	Total number of citations	All peer reviewed PARC publications are considered, including self-citations.
Media coverage	Number of articles	Number of articles in the media (international, national and local)

Communication products	Number of leaflets	Number of leaflets produced by PARC
	Number of videos	Number of videos produced by PARC
	Number of PARC Newsletters	Number of PARC Newsletters produced by PARC
	Number of PARC Science Digests	Number of PARC Science Digests produced by PARC
	Number of PARC Magazines	Number of PARC Magazines produced by PARC
	Number of policy briefs	Number of policy briefs produced by PARC
	Number of factsheets and infographics	Number of factsheets and infographics produced by PARC
	Number of research briefs	Number of research briefs produced by PARC
	Number of citizens	Number of citizens involved in the citizen survey
	Number of focus groups	Number of focus groups organised

In order to evaluate our communication products, we may also conduct surveys, online monitoring or focus groups.

17. Building capacities

A key component of PARC's communication and engagement strategy is the ongoing effort to build capacities across its diverse network of stakeholders. Targeted training activities have been developed for various audiences, including the PARC Junior Community, National Hubs, and other internal stakeholders. These trainings aim to strengthen communication skills, enhance technical knowledge, and promote consistent messaging throughout the consortium. In addition, internal capacity-building efforts have included hands-on sessions on digital tools, such as Figma for visual content creation, to improve design coherence and usability in communication products. These initiatives contribute to fostering a shared understanding of PARC's goals and equip partners with the necessary skills to support effective and impactful communication.

Additionally, one of the work packages, WP9, is responsible for organising trainings for scientists, while Task 3.2 oversees disseminating these through social media and the PARC website.

18. External communication rules, policies and procedures

Harmonised communication of the project outputs is a key element of success. The Partnership has many pathways for communication, both internal and externally. External communication occurs when PARC'S partners interact and communicate with stakeholders and entities outside the Partnership. It is important to regulate these channels to protect the interests of the Partnership. Communication policy and procedures should be written out in a clear, straightforward and concise language for all involved parties to understand how to act appropriately. The external communication policy, procedures and rules aim to provide the Consortium with guidance on handling information to avoid liability issues and prevent embarrassing or damaging situations that could harm the Partnership's reputation. Communication tools

under the umbrella of external communication like press releases, website, social media posts, newsletters, and others, play a vital role in shaping the image and reputation of the Partnership, as well as influencing present and future collaborators and stakeholders.

18.1. Rules for external communication

By adopting formal rules regarding external communication of information, we ensure that PARC maintains full control over its public image and reputation. These rules should be updated as necessary.

18.1.1. General

- Before engaging in any communication or dissemination activity expected to have significant media impact, the CT must inform the granting authority. In addition, all affiliated entities must inform the national grant signatory at the national level.
- When communicating on matters where the MB has adopted a position, each member shall represent the views of the MB, respecting the collegial approach intended in PARC. Members are free to express personal opinions but must clearly state that these do not necessarily reflect the views of the MB.
- Published PARC communication materials may be used at national or regional levels, provided they are adapted to suit national or regional needs.
- The official language for communication will be English.
- In accordance with European Commission guidelines, all dissemination materials issued by PARC must include the EU emblem and acknowledgement of EU funding.
- The PARC logo must appear on all dissemination materials, including websites, brochures, flyers, presentations, roll-up, posters—both printed and digital etc. A PARC branding and visual identity guideline will be provided.
- All communication and dissemination activities related to the action must be based on factually accurate information.

18.1.2. Authorised Spokespersons

Given the volume of information within the Partnership, it may be more efficient to appoint authorised spokespersons to handle specific types of inquiries. A member of the MB together with their alternate and in close collaboration with WP leaders, should be authorized to handle communication at the EU level with local media. At the national and regional levels, this role should be fulfilled by the NHCP. Designated spokespersons may delegate their role to the appropriate WP leader when more specific or technical information is required. This approach will help streamline and organize communication effectively.

18.1.3. Press releases

Press releases should be issued whenever the Partnership has important news to share, as they are one of the most effective ways to communicate key messages to the general public and other stakeholders. Press releases are versatile tools that can be distributed to media outlets, published online or shared via social media.

Each press release must be approved by the CT at the consortium level or by the NHCP at the national level, at least three working days prior to publication.

18.1.4. Newsletters, website and social media

PARC will issue two newsletters per year in English. Content for the newsletter will be proposed and prepared by the WP leaders and reviewed by WP3 to ensure compliance with the communication rules and alignment with PARC's communication objectives.

WP3 will also manage the content of the website and all social media accounts. Specific PARC hashtags should be used in all social media posts to maintain consistency and enhance visibility.

18.2. Policies for external communication

The communication plan will be updated and to ensure that all communication with the target audience complies with GDPR regulations.

Communication activities will aim to raise awareness among both general and specialized audiences about the EU policy areas addressed, such as Green Deal and the "One substance one assessment" approach.

All communication efforts will promote and uphold gender equality.

An open access policy will be followed for all dissemination activities.

19. Internal communication plan

The internal communication plan is included in the PARC's Handbook, as part of section 4.5 on communication and dissemination of results.

This section outlines internal communication procedures, provides rules and recommendations for the correct use of external communication tools, and details the available tools and working templates. It also includes guidance on how to produce and collect content from the partners—such as news for the website—how to track and report participation in conferences and workshops, and how to complete the internal newsletter template.

The Handbook also describes the mechanisms that will be used throughout the project to ensure the quality of communication and dissemination activities.

The role of the WP3, in cooperation with the CT, is crucial to ensure efficient, coordinated and harmonised communication among all PARC partners throughout the duration of the project.

20. Planning the long-term sustainability of communication products and tools

As part of PARC's exit strategy, communication products and tools need to be designed with long-term sustainability in mind, ensuring that the investments in visibility, knowledge-sharing, and branding are preserved after the project ends. The exit strategy should guarantee that these resources remain accessible, reusable, and embedded within lasting institutional frameworks, thereby securing PARC's visibility and impact beyond its lifetime. In line with the work carried out under Task 2.3 on sustainability communication products will be integrated into the broader framework of PARC activities (e.g. human biomonitoring, environmental monitoring, data storage and access, toxicity, safe and sustainable by design

an early warning system) so that they can continue to support policy, research, and stakeholder engagement in the long term.

Elements of the exit strategy for communication products and tools

- Hosting and maintenance PARC website
 - Explore options for the long-term hosting and maintenance of the PARC website, ideally within a stable EU institutional framework, or alternatively migrate the information into existing permanent platforms
 - Define responsibilities for technical updates and security after the project's end.
- Ownership and governance
 - Assign clear ownership of communication products (logos, templates, visuals, publications).
 - Establish agreements on how PARC's identity can be used in future projects or by partner institutions.
- Content continuity
 - Plan for archiving or migrating key resources (reports, policy briefs, infographics) to permanent repositories.
 - Keep knowledge bases updated or at least preserved for reference.
- Reusability of tools
 - Ensure design templates, branding guidelines, and visuals are stored in accessible formats for reuse.
 - Encourage partners to integrate these into their own communication workflows.
- Sustainability of impact
 - Identify long-term communication channels (e.g. newsletters, social media, institutional sites) where PARC outcomes can continue to be promoted.
 - Link PARC's communication products to future initiatives on chemical safety and environmental health.